

Data Sovereignty and CARE Principles

What — How — Why

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What do the CARE principles stand for?

The CARE principles stand for a way of handling research data that takes ethical issues, power dynamics, and historical contexts into account.

The CARE principles were developed in 2020 by the Global Indigenous Data Alliance for the management of indigenous data. However, they are also suitable more generally for an ethically sound approach to data. CARE stands for:

Collective Benefit

When data is collected and published, the individuals who contributed to the data pool should benefit from it in ways that align with their own values.

Authority to Control

The rights of individuals to their data should be recognized, and their control over the collection and use of the data should be strengthened. In the case of data from indigenous communities, these communities should be able to use the data autonomously and for the development of their policies.

Responsibility

Users of such data must demonstrate that they handle the data with respect and understanding and that they use it for the benefit and in the interests of the participants or the community. The use of the data should help improve and strengthen data literacy within the community itself.

Ethics

The rights and well-being of the individuals whose data is being used should be central at all stages of the data life cycle and throughout the entire data ecosystem. Data should be collected, assessed, and used in accordance with the ethical frameworks of the data-generating participants or community, thereby counteracting imbalances of power and resources.

Why are the CARE principles important?

CARE vs. FAIR

The CARE principles call for a conscious and ethically responsible approach to research data that goes beyond the legal framework of data protection and takes into account the data sovereignty of the individuals or communities that generate the data. They form an important complement to the FAIR principles, which focus primarily on data sharing and data reuse.

How can CARE be implemented?

Implementing the CARE principles in museums and libraries

In the context of memory institutions such as museums or libraries, the CARE principles contribute to the preparation and ethically responsible contextualization of historical collections and their often conflict-laden histories. So-called digital markers for identifying indigenous data (Traditional Knowledge Labels or Biocultural Labels) help to classify the data in collaboration with the community and provide information about further use of the data.

How can I implement CARE myself?

Individuals can also apply the CARE Principles in their own handling of data. This includes:

- conscious engagement and continuous reflection on the ethical aspects of handling data
- integrating the affected individuals or communities into the research process, especially regarding the (re)use of their data
- making the data accessible to the affected individuals or communities
- protecting the values and rights of individuals or communities when dealing with the data
- placing the data in historical and cultural context in accordance with the values of the individuals or community
- ensuring that measures for implementation are mentioned when drafting the consent form

Inform yourself

CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance

The website of the Global Indigenous Data Alliance contains useful information (in different languages):

Website: <https://www.gida-global.org/care>

Applying the CARE principles to research data:

Imeri, Sabine & Rizzolli, Michaela 2022. CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance: Eine Leitlinie für ethische Fragen im Umgang mit Forschungsdaten? *Das offene Bibliotheksjournal*, 9:2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5282/o-bib/5815>

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